

Progress Report for HELIOS Working Group 2 (WG2): Grant Period 1 (Sept 2023 – Sept 2024)

Overview

The following progress report for WG2 (Clinical Research and Patient Management), co-headed by Dr. Andreas Glenthøj and Dr. Anna Collado Gimbert, summarizes activities, key developments, and deliverables related to the objectives outlined in the HELIOS project. This report focuses on the Standardized Case Report Form (CRF), harmonization of clinical guidelines, new and emerging therapies, and future training plans, providing an update on activities in these domains for the first grant period.

Deliverables

D2.1 Standardized CRF for the Collection of Clinical and Laboratory Data

Progress in this area has focused on harmonizing CRFs from the RADeep, INHERENT, and other relevant initiatives. A comparison of CRFs between RADeep and INHERENT has been completed by Dr. Anna Collado Gimbert and Dr. Natasha Archer, and a harmonization effort has been initiated, with the goal of developing a unified CRF that incorporates best practices from both networks. This effort is still ongoing, and discussions on integrating this harmonized eCRF with national registries are planned for the upcoming meetings.

Key milestones:

- Comparative analysis between RADeep and INHERENT CRFs completed.
- Harmonization of the CRFs is in progress, with a draft expected by early 2025.

D2.2 Harmonized Guidelines for Clinical Management (≥ 4)

The harmonization of clinical guidelines is progressing steadily. In Year 1, the team has worked closely with the European Reference Network (ERN) on sickle cell disease. Dr. Anna Collado Gimbert has led this effort, which has laid the groundwork for harmonized clinical guidelines for sickle cell disease across multiple countries in Europe. These will form the foundation for broader harmonization efforts.

- Year 1 has focused on the ERN's sickle cell work, primarily led by Dr. Anna Collado Gimbert. Other clinical members of the WG2 are actively participating in the development of such consensus recommendations.
- In Year 2, the focus will shift toward unstable haemoglobin (Hb) variants, including consensus statements on diagnosis and management.

Next steps:

- Consensus statement on unstable Hb variants will commence in 2025.

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D2.3 Report on New and Emerging Therapies

WG2 launched a survey to map the current implementation of new therapies, particularly focusing on luspatercept and voxelotor. The survey, distributed via REDCap, has received 25 responses so far. Volunteers Dr. Adela Perolla and Dr. Geoffrey Cheminet have been leading the analysis of these responses and are preparing a preliminary report to present to the broader HELIOS group. This report will map the use of these therapies across participating centres and highlight any gaps in their implementation.

Key progress:

- REDCap survey received 25 responses, and analysis and drafting of the report is ongoing.

Training and Capacity Building

The first training school is scheduled for the second half of 2025 and will focus on the clinical management of Sickle Cell Disease specifically on Transcranial Doppler examination in paediatric patients. Dr Holger Cairo and Sotiroula Chatzimatthaiou have led this effort.

Simultaneously is under discussion the production of a series of webinars focusing on transfusion support in patients with haemoglobinopathies. The clinical team on WG2 is currently discussing the specific topics of interest and experts to lead the sessions.

Summary of Next Steps

1. Finalize the harmonization of CRFs for haemoglobinopathies and publish the eCRF.
2. Commence consensus statement on unstable Hb variants and initiate writing in 2025.
3. Continue analysis of REDCap survey results on new and emerging treatments.
4. Launch the first training school focused on clinical management - TCD Doppler in 2025.
5. Encourage volunteers and lead for the expert consensus on unstable Hb variants.
6. Develop the programme for the “Transfusion support” series of webinars.

